

Data sets: Quadruple Beltrami state in electron-depleted multi-ion dusty plasmas

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FIG. 1: The magnetic field variation against distance for $b_p = 1.301$, $b_{i_1} = 0.901$ and $b_{i_2} = 4.01$. The scale parameters are $\lambda_1 = 4.00696$, $\lambda_2 = 1.04669$, $\lambda_3 = 0.579174 + 1.02645i$ and $\lambda_4 = 0.579174 - 1.02645i$

I. OBJECTIVE

In the present work, a possibility of self-organization of electron-depleted multi-ion dusty plasmas has been presented. The system is self-organized to quadruple Beltrami state a higher order Beltrami state. This state has four scale parameters. The relaxed structures are dependent on the nature of scale parameters. The paramagnetic structures are formed, when the scale parameters are real and the diamagnetic structures are formed when the scale parameters are real as well as non-real. The system composed of three mobile components and one immobile component. There are four constants of motion in the system. The selection of Beltrami parameters play an important role in the formation of self-organized state. This study should be useful to describe the relaxed structures in astrophysical dusty plasma.

FIG. 2: The magnetic field variation against distance for $b_p = 2.701$, $b_{i_1} = 2.01$ and $b_{i_2} = 0.01$. The scale parameters are $\lambda_1 = 2.41236$, $\lambda_2 = 0.0347503$, $\lambda_3 = 1.31033$ and $\lambda_4 = 0.963561$.

FIG. 3: Characteristics of scale parameters for b_p , b_{i_1} and b_{i_2} . The colored regions are for $\Delta > 0$, while the white region is for $\Delta < 0$.